

The Influence of Green Brand Image, Satisfaction, Trust, on Loyalty Moderated by Environmental Ethics on Green Products in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of environmentally friendly brand image, satisfaction, trust, on loyalty moderated by environmental ethics towards green products in Indonesia. The research sample in this study were consumers who used and purchased Aqua gallons in 2024. This research method uses a quantitative approach with data collection techniques through questionnaires distributed to Aqua gallon users in Indonesia. The theoretical framework is built based on the latest literature review on environmentally friendly brand image, satisfaction, trust, loyalty, and environmental ethics on green products in Indonesia. The results of this study are expected to provide new insights into the effect of environmentally friendly brand image, satisfaction, trust, on loyalty moderated by environmental ethics towards green products in Indonesia. The practical implications of this study can help marketers and policy makers in designing effective communication strategies to increase purchases of green products in Indonesia.

KEYWORDS: Green Brand Image, Environmental Ethics, Loyalty, Satisfaction, Trust.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, there has been a significant change in people's perception of the environment. According to the IPCC report, the earth is already in a "code red" condition with a temperature increase of 1.5 degrees Celsius and climate disruption that threatens the well-being of humanity. (Kompas, 2021). In Indonesia, an environmental problem that has not been managed properly is the high amount of waste, where 5.2 million tons of the total 18.6 million tons of waste in 2021 were not managed properly (KLHK, 2021). This is in accordance with the results of research by the Tetra Pak Index 2019 that the environmental awareness of the Indonesian people is not in line with their attitude of caring for the environment. (CNN Indonesia, 2019).

Environmental awareness reflects an individual's level of understanding, concern and responsibility for the environment and the impact of their decisions and behavior in everyday life. (Alamsyah et al., 2020). Environmental awareness refers to an understanding and concern for environmental issues, such as pollution, climate change, and resource depletion (X. Chen et al., 2019). The tendency towards environmentally friendly consumption is considered as the main source of disclosure of environmental issues without affecting the market-based economy. (Zavali & Theodoropoulou, 2018). The emergence of the obligation to maintain environmental sustainability has an impact on consumer consumption patterns, therefore environmentally friendly products and sustainable consumption have become an international concern. (Li et al., 2016). Environmentally friendly consumption efforts are important to reduce negative impacts on the environment and encourage sustainable consumption patterns. (Chen dan Chai, 2010; Ghvanidze et al., 2016). This research focuses on environmental issues.

This concept is based on previous research which explains that there is a tendency for a significant influence between environmentally friendly brand image and consumer loyalty, in addition to that, environmentally friendly customer satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on environmentally friendly customer loyalty. (Sarko dan Sukawati, 2022). Increasing consumer perception of green brand image can help increase consumer loyalty in using environmentally friendly products. (Chrisjatmiko, 2018). Consumer awareness of environmental issues encourages healthy lifestyles by consuming products that contain safe, recyclable, non-toxic materials and use environmentally friendly packaging. This is in line with the trend of changing consumer behavior towards environmentally friendly consumption, where consumers are more aware of the environmental impact of their choices and are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. Green marketing and brand awareness also play an important role in influencing consumer behavior towards environmentally friendly consumption. (Petrescu et al., 2019). Green marketing has become a new focus in business, namely a strategic marketing approach that began to emerge and attract the attention of many parties at the end of the 20th century. (Mukonza dan Swarts, 2020). The term "green marketing" emerged as a response by

marketers and companies to changes in the business environment, particularly those related to environmental challenges. (Szabo & Webster, 2021).

In Indonesia, several companies have implemented green marketing in their marketing process. The results of this study are in accordance with a study conducted by Bastian (2014) who found that brand image has a positive effect on brand loyalty, which shows that brand image is formed because the company provides a good perception to its consumers, in addition to the company being able to manage and maintain good relationships with ADES consumers. Research conducted by Rizan et.al. (2012) found that brand image has a positive effect on brand loyalty of Teh Botol Sosro. The results of this study are in accordance with previous research found by Gadau (2016) who obtained the results of brand image with dimensions of company image, user image, product image together have a positive effect on consumer loyalty to the Body Mist product the Body Shop at Ambarukmo Plaza. Testing on brand image on customer loyalty shows that brand image has a significant effect on customer loyalty to The Body Shop products. Based on several studies above, it can be concluded that the most powerful value factor in building consumer eco-friendly brand awareness towards product perceptions that include performance, function, design, attractive shape, or taste suitability. Product attributes that are considered by consumers as eco-friendly attributes, such as the use of natural materials, eco-friendly production processes, and eco-friendly packaging. Research from Gemuruh Chairul Umam (2022) also supports this finding. The study found that green marketing and product quality have a positive and significant effect on green brand image. This green brand image is the consumer's perception of the brand as an environmentally friendly brand. Companies that innovate and maintain the environment of basic products will generate and increase consumer awareness of the company's products (Widodo dan Wahid, 2020).

This study is interested in explaining that there is a cognitive relationship related to brand image influencing consumer trust and loyalty. However, no one has conceptualized environmental ethics as a moderation, because there has been no research that uses environmental ethics as a moderation because this variable can strengthen the green brand, thus the research model conceptualized in this study explains the Influence of Environmentally Friendly Brand Image, Satisfaction, Trust, on Loyalty Moderated by Environmental Ethics in Mineral Water Companies in Indonesia.

In the context of green marketing, to gain competitive advantage, more and more companies are increasing customer satisfaction towards environmental needs by adopting green marketing strategies (Kang dan Hur, 2012). The overall function of positive attitudes towards green behavior greatly influences several behavioral intentions including purchase intention and willingness to pay a premium price (Han dan Ryu, 2009). The perception of value towards green products influences consumer trust in the product. so it is believed that the perception of value towards green products influences the perception of trust (Chen dan Chang, 2013).

Customer satisfaction is considered an important determinant of long-term consumer relationships (Zhang dan Prybutok, 2005). Consumer satisfaction with a company's products or services is considered the main key to a company's long-term success and competitiveness (Müller, 1991). The emergence of environmental understanding makes consumers not only willing to buy products with the least impact, but also more concerned about the environment (Chang dan Fong, 2010). Knowledge of green brands has a positive impact on attitudes towards green brands, and attitudes towards green brands have a positive impact on attitudes towards green brands have a positive impact on green product purchase intentions (Huang et al., 2014; Mohd Suki, 2016). In line with previous studies, Jabeen dan Kavitha (2020) found that there is a positive relationship between green marketing strategies and customer loyalty.

The concept of green marketing can be applied by companies through green loyalty. Green loyalty is a consumer commitment to repurchase products labeled as environmentally friendly (Martínez, 2015). Meanwhile, Chang dan Fong (2010), defines green loyalty as a customer's attitude to repurchase products labeled as environmentally friendly continuously. A loyal consumer is a consumer who always repurchases from the same company. Loyalty can hold fast to the commitment to be able to repurchase a very popular product or service in the future (Chang & Fong, 2010).

In addition to green satisfaction, green loyalty is also influenced by green brand image and green trust (Chen, 2010; Chen & Chang, 2012). Green brand image is a consumer's perception of the image of a brand with an environmentally friendly label (Chen, 2010). Furthermore, Chen (2010), states that green trust is the willingness of consumers to rely on a product, service with the belief that the brand can have a positive impact on its environment.

Research conducted by Chang dan Fong (2010) defines green customer loyalty as consumers who want to maintain relationships with companies involved in environmental protection or greening issues, and are committed to consistently repurchasing products in the future. It is true that green consumption, willingness to pay more, and intention to purchase green products have achieved

awareness among consumers, recognizing the value of high quality in environmental protection and they may choose green products because of their ethical beliefs (Hai Yen et al., 2023). However, research still limits its attention to consumer behavior and changes in their preferences (Akhtar et al., 2021).

The contribution of this study is the development of environmental ethics variables that have never been tested in developing countries before. This study will also discuss the factors that influence consumer loyalty in purchasing green products. This study is supported by several supporting conceptual variables including green brand image, satisfaction, trust, loyalty, and environmental ethics. This concept is based on previous research which explains that there is a tendency for a significant influence between green brand image and consumer loyalty, in addition, green customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on green customer loyalty (Sarko dan Sukawati, 2022). Increasing consumer perception of green brand image can help increase consumer loyalty in using environmentally friendly products (Chrisjatmiko, 2018).

THEORY AND HYPOTESIS

3.1 Literature Review

1. Green Brand Image

Green Brand Image refers to how consumers perceive a brand's environmental friendliness, this perception is often seen as an emotional connection to a particular brand within a company (Chen, 2010; Malik et al., 2012). In addition, green brand image can be understood as a series of ideas, thoughts, and understandings about a brand in the minds of customers, related to concerns for sustainability and environmental friendliness (Bashir et al., 2020). Promoting a company's environmental image is widely seen as a motivator for customers in today's business world. A company's environmental image held by stakeholders drives company expansion (Balmer & Greyser, 2006; Tiwari, 2023).

A company's green brand image reflects its stance on environmental protection and can differentiate it from competitors, meaning that a green brand image becomes a differentiator from other competitors. Thus, a strong brand image allows a company to be the first choice when consumers consider buying a product. Consumers who have beliefs about the environmental friendliness of a product are more likely to choose that product over competitors' products if they perceive no difference between the products. (Zhou et al., 2021). Companies will build their image well so that customers become loyal. Company image is an important trigger in building customer loyalty (Kotler, 2010). Increasing consumer perception of green brand image can help increase consumer loyalty in using environmentally friendly products (Chrisjatmiko, 2018).

2. Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is an important factor in building consumer loyalty towards environmentally friendly brands, products or services (Chen dan Chang, 2012). Some references define satisfaction as a feeling of disappointment or pleasure because there is a difference between reality and expectations in purchasing a product, this occurs when the product is purchased at each purchase, depending on several factors, including product quality, price, and promotion. The better the product quality, the higher the consumer satisfaction. Price also affects purchasing decisions, so the cheaper the price, the higher the purchasing decision and consumer satisfaction. Promotion also affects purchasing decisions, so the better the promotion, the higher the purchasing decision and consumer satisfaction (Kotler dan Keller, 2009; Oliver, 1999; Philip Kotler, 2015).

In the context of environmentally friendly products, satisfaction is one of the factors that influence purchasing decisions. Satisfaction occurs when purchasing a product and refers to the level of satisfaction related to consumption in meeting consumer expectations for the environment, future expectations, and environmentally friendly needs, making consumers not only willing to buy products that have the least impact, but also more concerned about the environment. (Chang & Fong, 2010). Satisfaction, perceived product quality is one form of customer evaluation of product quality in relation to environmental issues, and the quality of reliable and professional organic products also influences purchasing decisions (Chen et al., 2015; Tariq, 2014). The rise of environmental awareness has made consumers not only willing to buy products with minimal impact, but also more concerned about the environment (Chang dan Fong, 2010). Eco-friendly customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on eco-friendly customer loyalty. (Sarko dan Sukawati, 2022).

3. Trust

Consumer trust refers to the confidence that customers have in a company's compliance with truth, promises, verbal or written guarantees, and fulfillment of expectations and perceptions, as well as the fulfillment of consumer needs and desires (Ben Amor

dan Ben Yahia, 2022; Ebrahim, 2020; Huddin et al., 2024; Sichtmann, 2007). Trust plays a vital role in influencing consumer purchases, as it signifies confidence in the quality and reputation of products and services offered by a business (Bhaskar dan Kumar, 2016; Kim et al., 2012; Kassim dan Ismail, 2009).

Placing trust in the sustainable development of a product results from confidence in its environmental friendliness, reliability, and competence, which then leads to increased trust in the product (Chen, 2010). Consumer trust is difficult to achieve because it is not only achieved through the quality of environmentally friendly products but also how the product shows a positive impact on the environment (Mourad dan Ahmed, 2012). In building a strong relationship between consumers and brands, the role of trust is very important, and is positively related to brand loyalty (Lau, 1999).

4. Loyalty

Loyalty is a strong and deep commitment held by customers to continue to purchase or support their favorite products or services in the future and helps businesses reduce sales turnover and remain profitable. (Kotler, 2018; Willis, 2021; Zhou et al., 2021). Loyal customers are highly committed to repurchasing and continuing to use their preferred goods and services in the future, regardless of situational factors and marketing activities that may encourage switching behavior. (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2004). Customers who are loyal to a business feel better about it than disloyal customers or customers who switch, making them hesitant to switch. (Wu et al., 2021). Products or services in relation to the consumer's possibility of purchasing the product or service, as well as changes in consumption behavior that occur during the process, are known as the relationship between the product or service and the consumer's possibility of purchasing. (Kursan Milaković, 2021).

Brand loyalty is a pattern of repeat purchases due to a commitment to a particular brand. (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2004). Customer loyalty relates to the consistent selection of certain products and services over others. (Ngo et al., 2022). Generally, customers will be loyal and continue to purchase that brand even though customers have many alternative brands from competitors that offer superior products. (Loudon, 1993). Customer loyalty is the ultimate goal for many companies, because loyal customers will buy more and consume a large portion of the company's revenue. Loyal customers are less concerned with price than other customers. (Williams & Naumann, 2011). Loyal customers tend to make repeat purchases, stay committed to the product, buy other products from the same company, and they also recommend the product to others. (Griffin, 2016).

5. Environmental Ethics

Environmental ethics is the total perception of an organization towards the environment, such as environmental protection, environmental policy, environmental management, and the environment (Christinawati, 2018; Lin dan Yi-Fang, 2019). Environmental ethics serves as a conceptual foundation related to the ecological system and the preservation of life, as well as the concrete problems surrounding it, which lead to actions, attitudes, or policies that protect and maintain the ecosystem or its values (Rui & Lu, 2021). Ethical principles, values, and standards for environmental issues are the foundation of a company's environmental ethics (Ahmed et al., 1998). Companies that follow a culture of environmental ethics will be more valuable and are significant business drivers (Chang, 2011). In addition, companies that fulfill environmental responsibilities in operations and production also put pressure on other companies that are unwilling to carry out environmental responsibilities (Rui & Lu, 2021).

Environmental ethics culture is considered as an important internal resource that creates and enables businesses to implement innovative strategies and creativity that enhance green competitiveness (Guo et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2019). Companies that follow an environmental ethics culture will be more valuable and are significant business drivers (Chang, 2011). In addition, companies that fulfill environmental responsibilities in operations and production also put pressure on other companies that are not willing to carry out environmental responsibilities (Rui & Lu, 2021).

3.2 Hypothesis Development

1. The influence of green brand image on loyalty

In the study by Anam et al. (2020) it is explained that consumers can make purchases on a product by considering whether the product has a positive image or not. Building a good brand image can have an impact on consumer purchasing decisions for a particular product brand. Several studies have also revealed that environmental image can not only satisfy customers' environmental desires and environmentally friendly needs, but can also increase sales and improve their competitive advantage (Chen, 2008; Chen et al., 2006; Hu and Wall, 2005). This is confirmed by the research presented by Watson et al. (2024) showing that there is a positive and significant influence of environmentally friendly brand image on customer loyalty. This shows that green brand image plays an

important role in influencing consumer loyalty to products or services. Thus, the stronger the green brand image, the more likely consumers will be loyal to the brand. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

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H1: There is a positive relationship between green brand image and customer loyalty.

2. The influence of satisfaction and trust on loyalty

Based on the results of previous studies, it can be seen that the trust held by customers has a strong influence on forming loyalty (Ali Raza, 2012; Efendy dan Suryadinata, 2014; Hayu, 2014; Kuo, 2012). Research by Chinomona & Dubihlela (2014) related to consumer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty, found that consumer satisfaction is a crucial aspect in a competitive business environment and can increase consumer loyalty. Consumer satisfaction with a company's products or services is considered the main key to the company's success and competitiveness in the long term (Müller, 1991). This is confirmed by research of Rachbini et al. (2019) that trust has a positive impact on consumer trust. In the context of satisfaction. In the context of satisfaction research by Zhang et al. (2020) found that satisfaction has a potential impact on loyalty.

From the results of the research presented, it was found that satisfaction and trust have a positive influence on customer loyalty. This shows that the quality and ability of a brand that cares about customers affects customer satisfaction and trust in the brand, which affects customer loyalty. Thus, developing and improving satisfaction and trust can help strengthen the relationship between brands and customers, which affects customer loyalty. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H2: There is a positive relationship between satisfaction and loyalty

H3: There is a positive relationship between trust and loyalty

3. The influence of green brand image on satisfaction and trust

In the context of green brand image, research shows that green brand image has a positive effect on customer green satisfaction and green trust (Chen and Chai, 2010; Deniz and Onder, 2017). From the results of the study presented, it was found that green brand image has a positive effect on customer satisfaction and trust. This shows that the quality and ability of brands that care about the environment affect consumer satisfaction and trust in the brand. Thus, developing and improving green brand image can help strengthen the relationship between brands and consumers, which affects customer loyalty. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

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H4: There is a positive relationship between green brand image and satisfaction

H5: There is a positive relationship between green brand image and trust

4. The mediating role of satisfaction and trust in the relationship between green brand image and loyalty

Research by Ranjbarian et al. (2012) states that green trust mediates the impact of brand image on green satisfaction. This is also in line with the results of research conducted by Deniz and Onder (2017), which stated that customer trust and satisfaction have a

positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. Likewise, Chrisjatmiko's research (2018) stated that green loyalty is positively and significantly influenced by green Image, green Trust, and green Satisfaction. From the research results presented in the source, it was found that green brand image has a positive effect on green satisfaction and green trust, which shows that the green brand image owned by the product can have an impact on satisfaction and trust from the consumer side. Satisfaction and trust can affect customer loyalty through the relationship between green brand image, green satisfaction, and green trust. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

Many academics have proven the impact of environmental satisfaction on environmental loyalty, as in previous studies showing that environmental satisfaction has the potential to have a significant influence on customer loyalty (Chen & Chai, 2010; Chrisjatmiko, 2018; Martínez, 2015; Mutia Ayu Larasati, 2015; Pianroj, 2012). In addition, Maskur et al. (2017) stated that customer trust and satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. This study is in line with research conducted by Harumi (2016) which states that customer trust and satisfaction have a significant effect on customer loyalty. This is in line with the statement of Razak et al. (2016) who stated that in addition to customer satisfaction, the variable that influences customer loyalty is customer trust.

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H6: Trust mediates the relationship between green brand image and loyalty

H7: Satisfaction mediates the relationship between green brand image and loyalty

5. The moderating role of Environmental Ethics on the relationship between green brand image and satisfaction and loyalty

The results from research by Jati Waskito dan Harsono (2012) provide evidence of the relationship between business activities and environmental ethics by implementing regulatory compliance, green marketing, green product packaging and materials, and green financial reporting. Furthermore, research by Pemayun dan Suprapti (2016) proves that business environmental ethics have a significant impact on environmentally friendly products. In another study, it was emphasized that corporate environmental ethics are considered as one type of superior organizational culture that helps manage relationships with the environment and achieve environmentally friendly development (Wang, 2019). It is true that environmentally friendly consumption, willingness to pay more, and intention to purchase environmentally friendly products have achieved awareness among consumers, recognizing the value of high quality in environmental protection and they may choose environmentally friendly products because of their ethical beliefs (Hai Yen et al., 2023).

Based on the results of previous research, it can be seen that green products have a positive influence on sustainable competitiveness and competitive advantage through business environmental ethics. (Chen & Chai, 2010; Chrisjatmiko, 2018; Martínez, 2015; Mutia Ayu Larasati, 2015; Pianroj, 2012). This is confirmed by research results of Chang (2011), who found that green product innovation can mediate the positive relationship between environmental ethics and competitive advantage. However, green marketing failed to mediate the relationship between environmental ethics and competitive advantage.

Considering the above and emphasizing green consumption and sustainable development, the moderating role of Environmental Ethics on the relationship between green brand image and satisfaction, trust and loyalty can be an interesting research area to explore how environmental ethical values influence the relationship between these variables, and how this can affect consumer behavior and brand loyalty. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H8: Environmental ethics moderates the relationship between green brand image and satisfaction

H9: Environmental ethics moderates the relationship between green brand image and trust

METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method. The survey research method is a quantitative approach method that is useful for obtaining data that occurred in the past or present, regarding opinions, beliefs, characteristics, behaviors, variable relationships, and to test several hypotheses about sociological and psychological variables from samples taken from a certain population through social media or WhatsApp applications, systematically and structuredly describing the influence or causality of each variable to answer research questions. (Chen, 2024). In this study, the causal relationship studied is focused on exogenous variables, namely the influence of Green Brand Image on Consumer Loyalty of Bottled Drinking Water mediated by Satisfaction and Trust, and moderated by Environmental Ethics. The endogenous variable is Loyalty (Chen, 2024).

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

This study used an online questionnaire method to collect data from respondents who had or did not have previous experience in using electric vehicles. From the distribution process, a total of 400 respondent data were successfully collected and further processed for analysis in accordance with the research objectives. The questionnaire data collected from 400 respondents were classified based on area of residence, gender, and age. The majority of respondents were female, namely 220 people (55%), while male respondents numbered 180 people (45%). The largest number of respondents was 16-25 years old, namely 251 people (63%), followed by the age group > 35 years as many as 188 people (30%). The age group 31-35 years as many as 16 people (4%), and the age group 26-30 years as many as 15 people (3.8%). Respondents' occupations vary, with the largest number of students at 249 people (62%), followed by the Civil Servant occupation group at 72 people (18%), other occupation groups at 40 people (10%), private employee occupations at 28 people (7%), and the lowest with self-employed occupations at 11 people (3%). The respondents' residential areas are spread across several major cities in Indonesia. Central Java is the city with the largest number of respondents, namely 345 people (86%), followed by West Java 39 people (9.75%), Jakarta 7 people (2%), Yogyakarta 2 people (0.5%), and Banten and Kalimantan each 1 person (0.25%). This geographical distribution shows that respondents have quite diverse experiences and understandings regarding Aqua gallons. The results of the analysis in this study include instrument testing, model structure, mediation test, and moderation test. Instrument testing includes internal consistency reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity. Structural model testing includes examining R Square (R²), hypothesis testing, and path analysis of the regression model.

In this study, two types of validity tests were conducted, namely convergent validity test and discriminant validity test. By using threshold values for Factor Loading greater than 0.40, composite reliability (CR) more than 0.70, and average variance extracted (AVE) more than 0.50 (Bou & Satorra, 2010; Fornell & Larcker, 1981), The results of the convergent validity test show that the extracted indicators have good convergent validity values (Factor loading ranges from 0.705 to 0.918; CR between 0.937 to 0.952 which is greater than 0.70; AVE between 0.683 to 0.800; see Table 4.1. Thus, the extracted indicators are able to measure the construct effectively.

In the discriminant validity test, it is required that the square root value of AVE must be higher than the other correlation coefficients. (Bou & Satorra, 2010; Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The results of this test indicate that each measuring variable has adequate discriminant validity. The value of the relationship between similar variables is higher than the value of the relationship between different variables (see Table 4.2).

Table 4.1 Validity and Reliability Test Results

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	CR	AVE	Result
Green Brand Image	GBI1	0,843	0,948	0,753	Valid
	GBI2	0,864			Valid
	GBI3	0,878			Valid
	GBI4	0,902			Valid
	GBI5	0,880			Valid
	GBI6	0,838			Valid
Satisfaction	SFN1	0,867	0,944	0,736	Valid

	SFN2	0,910			Valid
	SFN3	0,903			Valid
	SFN4	0,785			Valid
	SFN5	0,831			Valid
	SFN6	0,845			Valid
Trust	TST1	0,889	0,952	0,768	Valid
	TST2	0,900			Valid
	TST3	0,901			Valid
	TST4	0,822			Valid
	TST5	0,873			Valid
	TST6	0,871			Valid
Loyalty	LYT1	0,871	0,937	0,683	Valid
	LYT2	0,820			Valid
	LYT3	0,797			Valid
	LYT4	0,851			Valid
	LYT5	0,871			Valid
	LYT6	0,855			Valid
	LYT7	0,705			Valid
Environmental Ethics	EVE1	0,881	0,952	0,800	Valid
	EVE2	0,890			Valid
	EVE3	0,911			Valid
	EVE4	0,918			Valid
	EVE5	0,872			Valid

Table 4.2 Variable Relationship Matrix

	EVE	GBI	LYT	SFN	TST
Environmental Ethics					
Green Brand Image	0,797				
Loyalty	0,781	0,825			
Satisfaction	0,748	0,799	0,872		
Trust	0,836	0,859	0,905	0,920	

The R-square analysis reveals the extent to which the independent variables contribute to the dependent variable in this study. The Loyalty variable has the highest R-square value, which is 0.760, indicating that 76% of its variance can be explained by the Green Brand Image variable. On the other hand, the Trust variable has an R-square value of 0.729, meaning that 72.9% of its variance can also be explained by Green Brand Image. Meanwhile, the Satisfaction variable recorded the lowest R-square value, which is 0.603, indicating that 60.3% of its variance can be explained by Green Brand Image. The remaining variance for all of these variables is explained by other factors outside this research model.

Table 4.3 Rsquare Test Results

	R Square
Loyalty	0,760
Satisfaction	0,603
Trust	0,729
Total	2,092

The results of the hypothesis testing show that Green Brand Image has a positive and significant effect on loyalty, with a t-statistic value of 3.773, which is greater than 1.96; therefore, Hypothesis 1 is accepted. Consumer Satisfaction also has a positive and significant effect on loyalty, with a t-statistic of 4.941 which exceeds 1.96, so Hypothesis 2 is accepted. Consumer trust shows an effect on loyalty, with a t-statistic of 5.408 which is greater than 1.96, so Hypothesis 3 is accepted. Green Brand Image has a significant impact on several variables in this study. Its effect on Consumer Satisfaction and Trust with t-statistic values of 7.998 and 11.042 respectively which are greater than 1.96; therefore Hypothesis 4 and Hypothesis 5 are accepted. In addition, satisfaction and trust as mediators between green brand image and loyalty have significant impacts on several variables in this study, respectively having t-statistic values of 4.644 and 4.760 which are greater than 1.96; therefore, Hypothesis 6 and Hypothesis 7 are accepted. However, Environmental Ethics does not function as a moderator in the relationship between Green Brand Image and Satisfaction and Trust, with t-statistic values of 1.229 and 1.769 respectively which are smaller than 1.96.

Table 4.4 Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Green Brand Image -> Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.145	0.146	0.031	4.644	0.000
Green Brand Image -> Trust -> Loyalty	0.210	0.208	0.044	4.760	0.000
GBI*EVE_1*Satisfaction	0.034	0.036	0.028	1.229	0.220
GBI*EVE_2*Trust	0.042	0.044	0.024	1.769	0.077
Green Brand Image -> Loyalty	0.204	0.206	0.054	3.773	0.000
Green Brand Image -> Satisfaction	0.496	0.496	0.062	7.998	0.000
Green Brand Image -> Trust	0.487	0.488	0.044	11.042	0.000
Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.293	0.295	0.059	4.941	0.000
Trust -> Loyalty	0.431	0.426	0.080	5.408	0.000

From the results of this hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that Green Brand Image, Satisfaction, and Consumer Trust have a positive influence on Loyalty. Satisfaction and Trust can also mediate Green Brand Image and Loyalty. However, environmental ethics do not function as a moderator in the relationship between Green Brand Image and Satisfaction and Trust in this study.

This finding indicates that marketing strategies that focus on improving Green Brand Image, Satisfaction, and Trust are effective in increasing customer Loyalty. However, the role of Environmental Ethics as a moderator is not significant in the context of the influence of Green Brand Image on Satisfaction and Trust. The results of this study provide important insights for marketers in designing effective communication and marketing strategies by utilizing the role of Green Brand Image.

The results of the regression model analysis shown in Table 4.4 indicate that Green Brand Image has a positive impact on Loyalty with a value of 0.204. Consumer Satisfaction also shows a positive influence on Loyalty with a value of 0.293. Meanwhile, Trust has a positive influence on Loyalty with a value of 0.431. The effect of Green Brand Image moderated by Environmental Ethics on Satisfaction and Trust respectively showed positive values of 0.034 and 0.042. This finding indicates that an increase in each of these variables tends to increase Loyalty.

Green Brand Image has a significant positive effect on several variables in this study. Its effect on Satisfaction and Trust is positive respectively by 0.496 and 0.487. In addition, Satisfaction and Trust also show a positive impact as a mediator on Green Brand Image and Loyalty with values of 0.145 and 0.210 respectively. These results confirm the importance of the role of Green Brand Image in influencing various aspects of consumer behavior.

Based on this analysis, it can be concluded that all variables studied have a positive effect on Loyalty. Green Brand Image, Satisfaction, and Consumer Trust have a significant positive effect on customer Loyalty. In addition, Satisfaction and Trust can function as mediators between Green Brand Image and Loyalty. However, Environmental Ethics does not act as a moderator in this relationship. These findings suggest that marketing strategies that enhance Green Brand Image, Satisfaction, and Trust can be effective in increasing customer Loyalty, although the role of Environmental Ethics in this context is not significant.

These results have important implications for marketing and communication strategies. Companies can focus on improving Green Brand Image, Consumer Satisfaction, and Trust will be effective in increasing customer Loyalty. Meanwhile, the role of Environmental Ethics as a moderator is not significant in this context, but it is still important to consider in the overall sustainability strategy of the company. By implementing these strategies, companies can strengthen customer loyalty and create long-term mutually beneficial relationships.

This study provides valuable insights for marketers in designing effective communication and marketing strategies. Leveraging Green Brand Image can be an effective strategy to improve, Consumer Satisfaction, and Trust will be effective in increasing customer Loyalty. Focusing on improving Green Brand Image, Consumer Satisfaction, and Trust can be key in building sustainable customer loyalty.

The mediating role of Green Brand Image in the influence of Satisfaction on Loyalty was tested using the Sobel test calculator and Smart PLS analysis. The results of the analysis show the coefficient of influence from X to M is 0.496 and from M to Y is 0.293 with standard errors of 0.062 and 0.059 respectively, resulting in a t-statistic value of 4.664 which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Based on these results, it can be concluded that Satisfaction has a significant role in mediating the influence of Green Brand Image on Loyalty.

Table 4.5 Mediation of the Influence of Green Brand Image, Satisfaction, Loyalty

Variabel	Input	
	Koefisien	Standart Error
GBI-SFN	0,496	0,062
SFN-LYT	0,293	0,059
Sobel Test	4,219	4,219

Table 4.6 Mediation of the Influence of Green Brand Image, Trust, Loyalty

Variabel	Input	
	Koefisien	Standart Error
GBI-TST	0,487	0,044
TST-LYT	0,431	0,431
Sobel Test	4,844	4,844

The mediating role of Trust in the influence of Green Brand Image on Loyalty was tested using the Sobel test calculator and Smart PLS processing results. The analysis showed the influence coefficient of X->M of 0.487 and M->Y of 0.431, with a standard error for X->M of 0.065, resulting in a calculated t value of 2.456, which exceeds the critical value of 1.96. Based on these results, it can be concluded that Trust has a significant role in mediating the influence of Green Brand Image on Loyalty.

The results of the moderation analysis showed that Environmental Ethics did not function as a moderator in the relationship between Green Brand Image and Satisfaction in this study, with a t-statistic value of 1.229 and a p-value of 0.220 and <0.1. This finding indicates that the influence of Green Brand Image on Loyalty is not significantly influenced by consumer Environmental Ethics. This may be due to other factors that are more dominant in influencing the effectiveness of marketing through Green Brand Image. Therefore, a separate evaluation is needed regarding the marketing aspects of environmentally friendly products in the Green Brand Image marketing strategy.

Picture 1. Outer Model
Data processed in SEM-PLS

CONCLUSIONS

This study reveals the significant role of Green Brand Image in influencing consumer Loyalty towards green products in Indonesia, with Satisfaction and Trust acting as mediators. Satisfaction, Trust, and Green Ethics are shown to have a positive and significant impact on Loyalty, highlighting the importance of marketing strategies that focus on these aspects. Interestingly, Environmental Ethics does not play a moderating role in the relationship between Green Brand Image and Loyalty, indicating that the influence of Green Brand Image is independent of the level of consumer environmental awareness. These findings provide important implications for marketing strategies in the bottled water industry, especially for environmentally friendly bottled water, where companies can leverage Green Brand Image to increase Trust and Satisfaction and build consumer Loyalty. However, it is important to note that although Green Attitude has a direct impact on Purchase Intention, marketing strategies related to this aspect should be considered separately from influencer marketing strategies.

The empirical contribution of this study to the digital marketing literature strengthens the theory of influencer marketing and emphasizes the importance of Green Brand Image strategies in the digital era. This study extends the understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying the effectiveness of Green Brand Image by uncovering the mediating role of Satisfaction and Trust, providing new insights into the cognitive and affective processes experienced by consumers in responding to marketing through Green Brand Image. The finding of the insignificant moderating effect of environmental ethics opens up opportunities for further academic discussion on the complexity of the interactions between environmental factors, green brand image, consumer satisfaction and trust, and loyalty in the context of green product marketing. The methodological contribution of this study lies in the demonstration of the application of SEM-PLS analysis in testing a complex model involving both mediation and moderation effects. Finally, this study highlights the importance of considering demographic factors in digital marketing research, which can encourage further investigation into how demographic differences affect the effectiveness of influencer marketing strategies and consumer purchase intentions in the context of specific products, such as electric vehicles.

Based on the findings of the study, bottled water companies are advised to focus their marketing strategies on leveraging a green brand image that is credible and relevant to their target market, given its significant positive impact on consumer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty. Companies need to ensure that green brand image can enhance positive consumer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty towards bottled water, given the significant mediating role of both aspects. Although environmental ethics was not found to significantly moderate the relationship between green brand image and satisfaction and trust, companies should still consider sustainability aspects in their marketing strategies because of its direct positive influence on consumer loyalty. Messages related to sustainability and the environmental benefits of bottled water can be integrated into the green brand image of bottled water, but should not be the main focus. Finally, further research is needed to explore other factors that may moderate the effectiveness of green brand image in the context of bottled water marketing, as well as to investigate how this strategy can be tailored to different consumer demographic characteristics.

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